

Package ‘avidaR’

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Title A Computational Biologist’s Toolkit To Get Data From 'avidaDB'

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Description Easy-to-use tools for performing complex queries on 'avidaDB', a semantic database that stores genomic and transcriptomic data of self-replicating computer programs (known as digital organisms) that mutate and evolve within a user-defined computational environment.

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convert_org_into_seq *Converts a genome instruction sequence into a digital organism file*

Description

Converts a genome instruction sequence into a digital organism file.

Usage

```
convert_org_into_seq(
    org,
    inst_set = "heads",
    save = FALSE,
    file_name = NULL,
    save_path = getwd(),
    format = "seq",
```

```

    silent = FALSE
  )

```

Arguments

org	Data Frame. Column names: "instruction".
inst_set	Name of the instruction set. It must be one of the following: "heads" (default), "heads-sex", or "transsmt". The names correspond to the instruction set configuration files (e.g., instset-heads.cfg for "heads").
save	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) indicating whether the output should or should not be saved to a file ("FALSE" by default).
file_name	String of characters representing the name of the file without any extension ("genome.seq" by default).
save_path	String of characters representing the name of the folder where the digital organism file will be saved.
format	String of characters representing the format of the file ("seq" by default).
silent	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide messages ("FALSE" by default).

Value

String of characters.

Examples

```

# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

sequence <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq[[1]]

convert_seq_into_org(genome_seq = sequence)

```

convert_seq_into_org *Converts a genome instruction sequence into a digital organism file*

Description

Converts a genome instruction sequence into a digital organism file.

Usage

```
convert_seq_into_org(
  genome_seq,
  inst_set = "heads",
  save = FALSE,
  file_name = NULL,
  save_path = getwd(),
  format = "org",
  silent = FALSE
)
```

Arguments

genome_seq	String of letters.
inst_set	Name of the instruction set. It must be one of the following: "heads" (default), "heads-sex", or "transsmi". The names correspond to the instruction set configuration files (e.g., instset-heads.cfg for "heads").
save	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) indicating whether the output should or should not be saved to a file ("FALSE" by default).
file_name	String of characters representing the name of the file without any extension ("organism.org" by default).
save_path	String of characters representing the name of the folder where the digital organism file will be saved.
format	String of characters representing the format of the file ("org" by default).
silent	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide messages ("FALSE" by default).

Value

Data frame. Column names: "instruction".

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
```

```
    user = "public_aida",
    password = "public_aida",
    repository = "aidaDB_test"
  )

sequence <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  triplestore = aidaDB
)$genome_seq[[1]]

convert_seq_into_org(genome_seq = sequence)
```

get_db_summary	<i>Get database summary</i>
----------------	-----------------------------

Description

Get a summary of the data stored.

Usage

```
get_db_summary(triplestore)
```

Arguments

triplestore Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame: Columns: "data type", "value".

Examples

```
aidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

aidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_aida",
  password = "public_aida",
  repository = "aidaDB_test"
)

get_db_summary(triplestore = aidaDB)
```

`get_docker_image_from_experiment_id`*Get docker image from experiment*

Description

get the docker image built to run the experiment, which guarantees reproducibility .

Usage

```
get_docker_image_from_experiment_id(avida_experiment_id, triplestore)
```

Arguments

`avida_experiment_id`

Integer or a vector of integer values.

`triplestore`

Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "avida_experiment_id" "docker_image_id" "id" "repo_digest"

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single paper
get_docker_image_from_experiment_id(
  avida_experiment_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one experiment
get_docker_image_from_experiment_id(
  avida_experiment_id = c(1, 2, 3, 4),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_doi_from_experiment_id
      Get doi from experiment
```

Description

Get the DOI of the scientific publication that documents the experiment carried out.

Usage

```
get_doi_from_experiment_id(avida_experiment_id, triplestore)
```

Arguments

`avida_experiment_id` Integer or a list of integer values.
`triplestore` Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "doi" "avida_experiment_id"

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single paper
get_doi_from_experiment_id(
  avida_experiment_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one experiment
get_doi_from_experiment_id(
  avida_experiment_id = c(1, 2, 4),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_experiment_id_from_organism_id  
    Get experiment from organism
```

Description

Get the experiment identifier and description from which a digital organism is derived.

Usage

```
get_experiment_id_from_organism_id(  
  organism_id,  
  triplestore,  
  description = FALSE  
)
```

Arguments

organism_id	Integer or a list of integer values.
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.
description	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide the description of the experiment (FALSE by default).

Value

Data frame. Columns: "organism_id" "avida_experiment_id"

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object  
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()  
  
# Set access options  
avidaDB$set_access_options(  
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",  
  user = "public_avida",  
  password = "public_avida",  
  repository = "avidaDB_test"  
)  
  
# Single organism  
get_experiment_id_from_organism_id(organism_id = 1, triplestore = avidaDB)  
  
# More than one organism  
get_experiment_id_from_organism_id(  
  organism_id = c(1, 2, 3),  
  triplestore = avidaDB  
)
```

`get_genome_id_from_genome_seq`*Get genome from genome sequence*

Description

Get the genome of a digital organism from the linear string of letters representing the instruction codes that make up its genome.

Usage

```
get_genome_id_from_genome_seq(genome_seq, triplestore)
```

Arguments

`genome_seq` String of letters or a list of strings
`triplestore` Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "genome_id" "genome_seq"

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Get sequence for genome_1
sequence <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq[1]

# Get genome id from sequence
get_genome_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_genome_id_from_logic_operation
```

Get genome from logic operations

Description

Get the genome of a digital organism that encodes a unique combination of logic operations for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_genome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation,
  seed_id = sample(1:1000, 1),
  genome_seq = FALSE,
  triplestore
)
```

Arguments

logic_operation	List of logical operations from the following set: "equals", "exclusive-or", "not-or", "and-not", "or", "orn-not", "and", "not-and", "not".
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000) or a vector of integer values. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If seed_id value is not specified, it returns data for a single randomly chosen seed_id value (between 1 and 1000).
genome_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column ("FALSE" by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_id", "genome_seq" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)
```

```

# Single logic operation
get_genome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = "not-or",
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one logic operation
get_genome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = c("not", "not-and"),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1
get_genome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = c("or", "equals", "and"),
  seed_id = 1,
  genome_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

```

```
get_genome_id_from_phenotype_id
```

Get genome from phenotype

Description

Get the genome of a digital organism that encodes a specific phenotype for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```

get_genome_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id,
  seed_id = sample(1:1000, 1),
  genome_seq = FALSE,
  triplestore
)

```

Arguments

phenotype_id	Integer or a list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000) or a vector of integer values. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If seed_id value is not specified, it returns data for a single randomly chosen seed_id value (between 1 and 1000).
genome_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column ("FALSE" by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "phenotype_id", "genome_seq" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single phenotype
get_genome_id_from_phenotype_id(phenotype_id = 1, triplestore = avidaDB)

# More than one phenotype
get_genome_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id = c(1, 2),
  genome_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seeds_4 and seed_5
get_genome_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id = c(1, 2),
  seed_id = c(4, 5),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

`get_genome_id_from_transcriptome_id`

Get genome from transcriptome

Description

Get the genome of a digital organism that executes a specific transcriptome for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_genome_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id,
  seed_id = FALSE,
  genome_seq = FALSE,
```

```

    triplestore
  )

```

Arguments

transcriptome_id	Integer or a list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
genome_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column ("FALSE" by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "transcriptome_id", "genome_seq" (optional).

Examples

```

# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single transcriptome
get_genome_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one transcriptome
get_genome_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = c(1, 2, 3),
  genome_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2
get_genome_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = 1,
  seed_id = c(1, 2),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

```

`get_genome_id_of_wild_type_organisms`*Get genomes of wild-type organisms*

Description

Get the genome of the digital organisms that were used as wild-type organisms to get their single-point mutants by calling the function `get_mutant_at_pos`.

Usage

```
get_genome_id_of_wild_type_organisms(triplestore)
```

Arguments

`triplestore` Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame: "genome_id_wild_type".

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

get_genome_id_of_wild_type_organisms(triplestore = avidaDB)
```

`get_genome_seq_from_genome_id`*Get genome sequence from genome*

Description

Get the linear string of letters representing the instruction codes that make up the genome of a digital organism from the id of the genome of a digital organism.

Usage

```
get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(genome_id, triplestore)
```

Arguments

`genome_id` Integer or a list of integer values.
`triplestore` Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "genome_id" "genome_seq"

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single genome
get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(1, triplestore = avidaDB)

# More than one genome
get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = c(1, 2, 3, 4),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_logic_operation_from_phenotype_id
```

Get the logic operations computed by a digital organism whose genome encodes a specific phenotype

Description

Get the logic operations encoded by a digital organism having the requested phenotype.

Usage

```
get_logic_operation_from_phenotype_id(  
  phenotype_id = FALSE,  
  phenotype_binary = FALSE,  
  triplestore  
)
```

Arguments

phenotype_id Integer, a vector of integers (from 0 to 511), or a logical value (if FALSE, the function returns the entire phenotype space).

phenotype_binary Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide phenotype_id in binary notation (FALSE by default).

triplestore Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "phenotype_id", "phenotype_binary" (optional), "equals", "exclusive-or", "not-or", "and-not", "or", "orn-not", "and", "not-and", "not"

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object  
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()  
  
# Set access options  
avidaDB$set_access_options(  
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",  
  user = "public_avida",  
  password = "public_avida",  
  repository = "avidaDB_test"  
)  
  
# One phenotype  
get_logic_operation_from_phenotype_id(  
  phenotype_id = 1,  
  phenotype_binary = TRUE,
```

```

    triplestore = avidaDB
  )

# More than one phenotype
get_logic_operation_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id = c(1,2,3),
  phenotype_binary = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# All phenotypes
get_logic_operation_from_phenotype_id(triplestore = avidaDB)

```

get_mutant_at_pos *Get single-point mutants of wild-type organisms*

Description

Get the genome sequence of a digital organism (i.e., wild-type) and its single-point mutants.

Usage

```

get_mutant_at_pos(
  genome_id = NULL,
  inst_replaced = NULL,
  inst_replaced_by = NULL,
  pos = NULL,
  triplestore
)

```

Arguments

genome_id	Integer or a list of integer values. If not specified, the function will return the single-point mutants of a randomly chosen wild-type organism.
inst_replaced	A letter representing the instruction of the genome sequence of the wild-type organism to be mutated. If not specified, the function will return the single-point mutants that have replaced the letter that the genome of the wild-type organism carried at that position (if the position is specified, otherwise it will return the mutations located on all positions) by the letter indicated in the argument inst_replaced_by (if specified, otherwise it will return all the mutants at that position on the genome of the wild type organism).
inst_replaced_by	A letter representing the instruction of the genome of the single-point mutant that have replaced the instruction of the genome of the wild-type organism. If not specified, the function will return all single-point mutants that have replaced the letter indicated in the argument inst_replaced (if specified, otherwise it will

	return all the mutants at that position on the genome of the wild type organism) of the genome of the wild-type organism at that position (if the position is specified, otherwise it will return the mutations located on all positions).
pos	Integer representing the position of the single-point mutation along the genome of a digital organism (from 1 to 100 for a genome length of 100 instructions). If not specified, the function will return all single-point mutants of the genome of the wild-type organism.
triplestore	Object of class <code>triplestore_access</code> which manages database access.

Value

Data frame: Columns: "genome_id_wild_type", "genome_seq_wild_type", "genome_id_mutant", "genome_seq_mutant", "pos".

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

get_mutant_at_pos(
  genome_id = 582,
  inst_replaced = 'o',
  inst_replaced_by = 'a',
  pos = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB)
```

`get_phenotype_id_from_genome_id`
Get phenotype from genome

Description

Get the phenotype encoded by the genome of a digital organism for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_phenotype_id_from_genome_id(  
  genome_id,  
  seed_id = FALSE,  
  phenotype_binary = FALSE,  
  triplestore  
)
```

Arguments

<code>genome_id</code>	Integer or a list of integer values.
<code>seed_id</code>	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
<code>phenotype_binary</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide <code>phenotype_id</code> in binary notation (FALSE by default).
<code>triplestore</code>	Object of class <code>triplestore_access</code> which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_id", "phenotype_id" "phenotype_binary" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object  
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()  
  
# Set access options  
avidaDB$set_access_options(  
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",  
  user = "public_avida",  
  password = "public_avida",  
  repository = "avidaDB_test"  
)  
  
# Single genome  
get_phenotype_id_from_genome_id(genome_id = 1, triplestore = avidaDB)  
  
# More than one genome at seed_1  
get_phenotype_id_from_genome_id(  
  genome_id = c(1, 2, 3),  
  seed_id = 1,  
  triplestore = avidaDB  
)  
  
# More than one genome at more than one seed (e.g., seed_3 and seed_4)
```

```

get_phenotype_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  seed_id = c(3, 4),
  phenotype_binary = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

```

```

get_phenotype_id_from_genome_seq
  Get phenotype from genome sequence

```

Description

Get the phenotype encoded by the instruction sequence constituting the genome of a digital organism for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```

get_phenotype_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq,
  seed_id = FALSE,
  genome_id = FALSE,
  phenotype_binary = FALSE,
  triplestore
)

```

Arguments

genome_seq	String of letters or a list of strings.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
genome_id	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide genome_id (FALSE by default).
phenotype_binary	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide phenotype_id in binary notation (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_id" (optional), "genome_seq", "phenotype_id", "phenotype_binary" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Get sequences for genomes_1 and genome_2
sequence1 <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq[1]

sequence2 <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 2,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq[1]

# Single genome
get_phenotype_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one genome
get_phenotype_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = c(sequence1, sequence2),
  genome_id = TRUE,
  phenotype_binary = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2
get_phenotype_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence2,
  seed_id = c(1, 2),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

get_phenotype_id_from_logic_operation

Get phenotype from logic operations

Description

Get the phenotype encoded by the genome of a digital organism that is specified by a unique combination of logic operations.

Usage

```
get_phenotype_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation,
  phenotype_binary = FALSE,
  triplestore
)
```

Arguments

`logic_operation` List of logical functions from the following set: "equals", "exclusive-or", "not-or", "and-not", "or", "orn-not", "and", "not-and", "not".

`phenotype_binary` Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide the phenotype in binary notation (FALSE by default).

`triplestore` Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "phenotype_id", "phenotype_binary" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single logic operation
get_phenotype_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = "not-or",
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one logic operation
ops <- c("equals", "exclusive or", "not-or", "and-not", "or", "orn-not")

get_phenotype_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = ops,
```

```
    phenotype_binary = TRUE,  
    triplestore = avidaDB  
  )
```

get_phenotype_id_from_transcriptome_id
Get phenotype from transcriptome

Description

Get the phenotype encoded by the genome of a digital organism that executes a specific transcriptome for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_phenotype_id_from_transcriptome_id(  
  transcriptome_id,  
  seed_id = FALSE,  
  phenotype_binary = FALSE,  
  triplestore  
)
```

Arguments

transcriptome_id	Integer or list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
phenotype_binary	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide phenotype in binary notation (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "transcriptome_id", "phenotype_id", "phenotype_binary" (optional)

Examples

```

# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single transcriptome
get_phenotype_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = 53674,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one transcriptome
get_phenotype_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = c(53674, 1666099),
  phenotype_binary = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_3
get_phenotype_id_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = 53674, seed_id = c(1,3),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

```

```
get_tandem_id_from_genome_id
```

Get tandem repeat from genome

Description

Get the tandem repeat contained in the transcriptome of a digital organism having a specific genome.

Usage

```

get_tandem_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id,
  seed_id = FALSE,
  tandem_seq = FALSE,
  tandem_pos = FALSE,
  triplestore
)

```

Arguments

genome_id	Integer or a list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
tandem_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
tandem_pos	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_id", "tandem_id", "tandem_seq" (optional), "tandem_pos" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single genome
get_tandem_id_from_genome_id(genome_id = 1, triplestore = avidaDB)

# More than one genome
get_tandem_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = c(1, 2, 3),
  tandem_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1, seed_3 and seed_5
get_tandem_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 2,
  seed_id = c(1, 3, 5),
  tandem_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_tandem_id_from_genome_seq
```

Get tandem repeat from genome sequence

Description

Get the tandem repeat contained in the transcriptome of a digital organism having a specific linear string of letters representing the instruction codes that make up its genome.

Usage

```
get_tandem_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq,
  seed_id = FALSE,
  tandem_seq = FALSE,
  tandem_pos = FALSE,
  triplestore
)
```

Arguments

genome_seq	String of letters or a list of strings.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
tandem_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
tandem_pos	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Column: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_id", "tandem_id", "tandem_seq" (optional), "tandem_pos" (optional)."

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
```

```
)

# Get sequences for genomes 1 and 2
sequence1 <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq

sequence2 <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  2,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq

# Single genome
get_tandem_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one genome
get_tandem_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = c(sequence1, sequence2),
  tandem_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2
get_tandem_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence2,
  seed_id = c(1,2),
  tandem_seq = TRUE,
  tandem_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

get_tandem_id_from_logic_operation

Get tandem repeat from logic operations

Description

Get the tandem repeat contained in the transcriptome of a digital organism that executes a specific combination of logic operations.

Usage

```
get_tandem_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation,
  seed_id = sample(1:1000, 1),
```

```

    tandem_seq = FALSE,
    tandem_pos = FALSE,
    triplestore
  )

```

Arguments

<code>logic_operation</code>	List of logical functions from the following set: "equals", "exclusive or", "not-or", "and-not", "or", "orn-not", "and", "not-and", "not".
<code>seed_id</code>	Integer (from 1 to 1000) or a vector of integer values. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If <code>seed_id</code> value is not specified, it returns data for a single randomly chosen <code>seed_id</code> value (between 1 and 1000).
<code>tandem_seq</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>tandem_pos</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>triplestore</code>	Object of class <code>triplestore_access</code> which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "tandem_id", "tandem_seq" (optional), "tandem_pos" (optional).

Examples

```

# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single logic operation
get_tandem_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = "not",
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one logic operation
get_tandem_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = c("not", "and"),
  tandem_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2

```

```

get_tandem_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = c("not", "and"),
  tandem_seq = TRUE,
  tandem_pos = TRUE,
  seed_id = c(1,2),
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

```

```
get_tandem_id_from_phenotype_id
```

Get tandem repeat from phenotype

Description

Get the tandem repeat contained in the transcriptome of a digital organism that encodes a specific phenotype for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```

get_tandem_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id,
  seed_id = sample(1:1000, 1),
  tandem_seq = FALSE,
  tandem_pos = FALSE,
  triplestore
)

```

Arguments

phenotype_id	Integer or list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000) or a vector of integer values. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If seed_id value is not specified, it returns data for a single randomly chosen seed_id value (between 1 and 1000).
tandem_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
tandem_pos	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Column: "seed_id" (optional), "phenotype_id", "tandem_id", "tandem_seq" (optional), "tandem_pos (optional)."

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single phenotype
get_tandem_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id = 8, tandem_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one phenotype at seed_1
get_tandem_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id = c(2, 4, 8), seed_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2
get_tandem_id_from_phenotype_id(
  phenotype_id = 1,
  seed_id = c(1, 2),
  tandem_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

`get_tandem_seq_from_tandem_id`

Get the tandem repeat sequence from tandem repeat

Description

Get the tandem sequence from the tandem repeat contained in the transcriptome of a digital organism for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_tandem_seq_from_tandem_id(
  tandem_id,
  seed_id = FALSE,
  genome_id = FALSE,
```

```

    tandem_pos = FALSE,
    triplestore
  )

```

Arguments

tandem_id	Integer or a list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
genome_id	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
tandem_pos	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "tandem_id", "tandem_seq", "tandem_pos" (optional), "genome_id" (optional).

Examples

```

# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single tandem
get_tandem_seq_from_tandem_id(
  tandem_id = 6336945,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one tandem at seed_1
get_tandem_seq_from_tandem_id(
  tandem_id = c(6336945, 2520963, 2520963),
  seed_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_3 and seed_5
get_tandem_seq_from_tandem_id(
  tandem_id = 6336945,

```

```

seed_id = c(1, 3),
tandem_pos = TRUE,
genome_id = TRUE,
triplestore = avidaDB
)

```

```
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_id
```

Get transcriptome from genome

Description

Get the transcriptome of a digital organism having a specific genome for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```

get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id,
  seed_id = FALSE,
  transcriptome_seq = FALSE,
  transcriptome_pos = FALSE,
  genome_seq = FALSE,
  triplestore
)

```

Arguments

<code>genome_id</code>	Integer or list of integer values.
<code>seed_id</code>	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
<code>transcriptome_seq</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>transcriptome_pos</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>genome_seq</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>triplestore</code>	Object of class <code>triplestore_access</code> which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_id", "genome_seq" (optional), "transcriptome_id", "transcriptome_seq" (optional), "transcriptome_pos" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Singel genome
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one genome
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = c(1, 2),
  transcriptome_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_3
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 2,
  seed_id = c(1, 3),
  transcriptome_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_seq

Get transcriptome from genome sequence

Description

Get the transcriptome of a digital organism having a specific linear string of letters representing the instruction codes that make up its genome for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq,
  seed_id = FALSE,
```

```

    transcriptome_seq = FALSE,
    transcriptome_pos = FALSE,
    genome_id = FALSE,
    triplestore
  )

```

Arguments

<code>genome_seq</code>	String of letters or a list of strings.
<code>seed_id</code>	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
<code>transcriptome_seq</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>transcriptome_pos</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>genome_id</code>	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
<code>triplestore</code>	Object of class <code>triplestore_access</code> which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "genome_seq", "transcriptome_id", "transcriptome_seq" (optional), "transcriptome_pos" (optional).

Examples

```

# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Get sequences for genome_1 and genome_2
sequence1 <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq[1]

sequence2 <- get_genome_seq_from_genome_id(
  genome_id = 2,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)$genome_seq[1]

```

```
# Single genome
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one genome
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = c(sequence1, sequence2),
  transcriptome_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2
get_transcriptome_id_from_genome_seq(
  genome_seq = sequence2,
  seed_id = c(1,2),
  transcriptome_seq = TRUE,
  transcriptome_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_transcriptome_id_from_logic_operation
  Get transcriptome from logic operations
```

Description

Get the transcriptome of a digital organism that executes a specific combination of logic operations for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_transcriptome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation,
  seed_id = sample(1:1000, 1),
  transcriptome_seq = FALSE,
  transcriptome_pos = FALSE,
  triplestore
)
```

Arguments

logic_operation

List of logical functions from the following set: "equals", "exclusive or", "not-or", "and-not", "or", "orn-not", "and", "not-and", "not".

seed_id Integer (from 1 to 1000) or a vector of integer values. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If **seed_id** value is not specified, it returns data for a single randomly chosen **seed_id** value (between 1 and 1000).

transcriptome_seq Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).

transcriptome_pos Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).

triplestore Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "transcriptome_id", "transcriptome_seq" (optional), "transcriptome_pos" (optional)

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single logic operation
get_transcriptome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = "not",
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one logic operation
get_transcriptome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = c("not", "and"),
  transcriptome_seq = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_2
get_transcriptome_id_from_logic_operation(
  logic_operation = c("not", "and"),
  seed_id = c(1,2),
  transcriptome_seq = TRUE,
  transcriptome_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

```
get_transcriptome_id_from_phenotype_id
```

Get transcriptome from phenotype

Description

Get the transcriptome of a digital organism whose genome encodes a specific phenotype for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_transcriptome_id_from_phenotype_id(  
  phenotype_id,  
  seed_id = sample(1:1000, 1),  
  transcriptome_seq = FALSE,  
  transcriptome_pos = FALSE,  
  phenotype_binary = FALSE,  
  triplestore  
)
```

Arguments

`phenotype_id` Integer or list of integer values.

`seed_id` Integer (from 1 to 1000) or a vector of integer values. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If `seed_id` value is not specified, it returns data for a single randomly chosen `seed_id` value (between 1 and 1000).

`transcriptome_seq`
Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).

`transcriptome_pos`
Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).

`phenotype_binary`
Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).

`triplestore` Object of class `triplestore_access` which manages database access.

Value

Data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "transcriptome_id", "transcriptome_seq" (optional), "transcriptome_pos" (optional), "phenotype_id", "phenotype_binary" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object  
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()  
  
# Set access options
```

```
avidaDB$set_access_options(  
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",  
  user = "public_avida",  
  password = "public_avida",  
  repository = "avidaDB_test"  
)  
  
# Single phenotype  
get_transcriptome_id_from_phenotype_id(  
  phenotype_id = 1,  
  transcriptome_seq = TRUE,  
  triplestore = avidaDB  
)  
  
# More than one phenotype at seed_1  
get_transcriptome_id_from_phenotype_id(  
  phenotype_id = c(1, 2), seed_id = 1,  
  triplestore = avidaDB  
)  
  
# At seed_1 and seed_2  
get_transcriptome_id_from_phenotype_id(  
  phenotype_id = 1,  
  seed_id = c(1, 2),  
  transcriptome_pos = TRUE,  
  triplestore = avidaDB  
)
```

```
get_transcriptome_seq_from_transcriptome_id  
  Get transcriptome sequence from transcriptome
```

Description

Get the transcriptome sequence of the transcriptome executed by a digital organism for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
get_transcriptome_seq_from_transcriptome_id(  
  transcriptome_id,  
  seed_id = FALSE,  
  transcriptome_pos = FALSE,  
  genome_seq = FALSE,  
  triplestore  
)
```

Arguments

transcriptome_id	Integer or list of integer values.
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
transcriptome_pos	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
genome_seq	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide this column (FALSE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Value

data frame. Columns: "seed_id" (optional), "transcriptome_id", "transcriptome_seq", "transcriptome_pos" (optional), "genome_seq" (optional).

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
avidaDB <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
avidaDB$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# Single transcriptome
get_transcriptome_seq_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = 53674,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# More than one transcriptome at seed_1
get_transcriptome_seq_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = c(53674, 1666099),
  seed_id = 1,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)

# At seed_1 and seed_3
get_transcriptome_seq_from_transcriptome_id(
  transcriptome_id = 2,
  seed_id = c(1, 3),
  transcriptome_pos = TRUE,
  triplestore = avidaDB
)
```

)

instruction_set	<i>Get the genetic language of Avida</i>
-----------------	--

Description

List of the instruction codes comprising the genetic language of digital organisms in Avida.

Usage

```
instruction_set(inst_set = "heads")
```

Arguments

inst_set	Name of the instruction set. It must be one of the following: "heads" (default), "heads-sex", or "transsmt". The names correspond to the instruction set configuration files (e.g., instset-heads.cfg for "heads").
----------	---

Value

Data frame. Columns: "instruction", "letter", "color"

logic_operation	<i>Get the list of logic operations that a digital organism can compute</i>
-----------------	---

Description

List of the logic operations that a digital organism can execute.

Usage

```
logic_operation()
```

Value

Vector of character.

plot_transcriptome *Get a plot of the transcriptome as a chord diagram*

Description

Get a plot of the transcriptome executed by a digital organism for a list of seeds used for starting the pseudo-random number generator (i.e., a set of environments).

Usage

```
plot_transcriptome(
  transcriptome_id,
  seed_id = NULL,
  inst_set = "heads",
  save = FALSE,
  file_name = NULL,
  save_path = "~/transcriptome@chords",
  format = "svg",
  silent = FALSE,
  triplestore
)
```

Arguments

transcriptome_id	Integer
seed_id	Integer (from 1 to 1000), a vector of integer values, or a logical value. This integer is used for starting the pseudo-random number generator that represents the environment experiencing a digital organism. If a logical value is used, TRUE returns data found in all environments and FALSE (by default) returns only distinct data regardless of the seed.
inst_set	Name of the instruction set. It must be one of the following: "heads" (default), "heads-sex", or "transsmt". The names correspond to the instruction set configuration files (e.g., instset-heads.cfg for "heads").
save	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to save the plot (FALSE by default).
file_name	String of characters indicating the name of the file to be saved (without extension).
save_path	String of characters indicating the name of the folder where the file will be saved.
format	String of characters indicating the format of the file ("pdf" and "svg" are currently supported).
silent	Logical value (TRUE/FALSE) to show/hide messages (TRUE by default).
triplestore	Object of class triplestore_access which manages database access.

Examples

```
# Create triplestore object
triplestore <- triplestore_access$new()

# Set access options
triplestore$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_avida",
  password = "public_avida",
  repository = "avidaDB_test"
)

# plot transcriptome 53674 at seed_1 and save to disk in pdf format
plot_transcriptome(
  transcriptome_id = 53674,
  seed_id = 1,
  save = FALSE,
  save_path = getwd(),
  format = "pdf",
  triplestore = triplestore
)
```

triplestore_access *Class to manage triplestore access options*

Description

Class to manage triplestore access options

Methods

Public methods:

- `triplestore_access$new()`
- `triplestore_access$get_access_options()`
- `triplestore_access$set_access_options()`
- `triplestore_access$submit_query()`
- `triplestore_access$ontology()`
- `triplestore_access$clone()`

Method `new()`: Create and initialize the object.

Usage:

```
triplestore_access$new()
```

Returns: Object of class `triplestore_access`.

Method `get_access_options()`: Get access options

Usage:

```
triplestore_access$get_access_options()
```

Returns: list containing URL of the API server, user credentials, repository name, authentication status, and SPARQL protocol version

Method `set_access_options()`: Set authentication access options for graphdb triplestore

Usage:

```
triplestore_access$set_access_options(
  url = NULL,
  user = NULL,
  password = NULL,
  repository = NULL,
  timeout = 100
)
```

Arguments:

`url` String containing the URL of the triplestore server

`user` String containing the username if authentication is needed

`password` String containing the password if authentication is needed

`repository` String containing the ID of the repository to which you want to connect to

`timeout` Connection timeout limit in seconds used for queries

Method `submit_query()`: Submit a SPARQL query to the triplestore to obtain data

Usage:

```
triplestore_access$submit_query(query)
```

Arguments:

`query` String containing the SPARQL query to retrieve data

Method `ontology()`: Show ontology information

Usage:

```
triplestore_access$ontology()
```

Returns: List containing title, description and versionIRI of the ontology

Method `clone()`: The objects of this class are cloneable with this method.

Usage:

```
triplestore_access$clone(deep = FALSE)
```

Arguments:

`deep` Whether to make a deep clone.

Examples

```
# Create object triplestore
triplestore <- triplestore_access$new()
```

```
# Set options to access a specific triple-store implemented in GraphDB

triplestore$set_access_options(
  url = "https://graphdb.fortunalab.org",
  user = "public_aida",
  password = "public_aida",
  repository = "aidaDB_test"
)

# Show current access options

triplestore$get_access_options()

# Querying data with SPARQL

triplestore$submit_query('PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
  PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
  select ?tandem_id where {
    ?digital_tandem_repeat rdfs:label "digital tandem repeat"@en .
    ?tandem_id a ?digital_tandem_repeat .
  } limit 10')
```

```
# Show ontology info

triplestore$ontology()
```

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